

A Note on the Smarandache Near-To-Primorial Function

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In a brief paper passed on to the author[1], Michael R. Mudge used the definition of the Primorial function:

Definition: For p any prime, the Primorial function of p , p^* is the product of all prime numbers less than or equal to p .

Examples:

$$3^* = 2 * 3 = 6$$

$$11^* = 2 * 3 * 5 * 7 * 11 = 2310$$

To define the Smarandache Near-To-Primorial Function $SPr(n)$

Definition: For n a positive integer, the Smarandache Near-To-Primorial Function $SPr(n)$ is the smallest prime p such that either p^* or $p^* + 1$ or $p^* - 1$ is divisible by n .

A table of initial values is also given

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	...	59
$SPr(n)$	2	2	2	5	3	3	3	5	?	5	11	...	13

and the following questions posed:

- 1) Is $SPr(n)$ defined for all positive integers n ?
- 2) What is the distribution of values of $SPr(n)$?
- 3) Is this problem fundamentally altered by replacing $p^* \pm 1$ by $p^* \pm k$ for $k = 3, 5, \dots$?

The purpose of this paper is to address these questions.

We start with a simple but important result that is presented in the form of a lemma.

Lemma 1: If the prime factorization of n contains more than one instance of a prime as a factor, then n cannot divide q^* for q any prime.

Proof: Suppose that n contains at least one prime factor to a power greater than one, for reference purposes, call that prime p_1 . The list of prime factors of n contains a largest

prime and we can call that prime p_2 . If we choose another arbitrary prime q , there are two cases to consider.

Case 1: $q < p_2$. Then p_2 cannot divide q^* , as q^* contains no instances of p_2 by definition.

Case 2: $q \geq p_2$. In this case, each prime factor of n will divide q^* , but since p_1 appears only once in q^* , p_1^2 cannot divide q^* . Therefore, n cannot divide q^* as well. \square

We are now in a position to answer the first question.

Theorem 1: If n contains more than one instance of 2 as a factor, then $SPr(n)$ does not exist.

Proof: Choose n to be a number having more than one instance of 2 as a factor. By lemma 1, there is no prime q such that n divides q^* . Furthermore, since 2 is a prime, q^* is always even. Therefore, $q^* \pm 1$ is always odd and n cannot evenly divide it. \square

The negative answer to the first question also points out two errors in the Mudge table. $SPr(4)$ and $SPr(8)$ do not exist, and an inspection of the given values verifies this. The Primorial of 5 is $2*3*5 = 30$ and no element in the set $\{ 29,30,31 \}$ is evenly divisible by 4.

By definition, the range of $SPr(n)$ is a set of prime numbers. The obvious question is then whether the range of $SPr(n)$ is in fact the set of all prime numbers, and we state the answer as a theorem.

Theorem 2: The range of $SPr(n)$ is the set of all prime numbers.

Proof: The first few values are by inspection.

$$SPr(1) = 2, SPr(5) = 3, SPr(10) = 5$$

Choose an arbitrary prime $p > 5$ and construct the number $p^* - 1$. Obviously, $p^* - 1$ divides $p^* - 1$. It is also clear that there is no prime $q < p$ such that q^* , $q^* + 1$ or $q^* - 1$ is divisible by $p^* - 1$. Therefore, $SPr(p^* - 1) = p$ and p is in the range of $SPr(n)$. \square

Which answers the second question posed by M. Mudge.

It is easy to establish an algorithmic process to determine if $SPr(n)$ is defined for values of n containing more than one instance of a prime greater than 2.

The first step is to prove another lemma.

Lemma 2: If n contains a prime p that appears more than once as a factor of n , and q is any prime $q \geq p$, then n does not divide $q^* \pm 1$.

Proof: Let n , p and q have the stated properties. Clearly, p divides q^* and since q is greater than 1, p cannot divide $q^* \pm 1$, forcing the conclusion that n cannot divide $q^* \pm 1$ as well. Combining this with lemma 1 gives the desired result. \square

Corollary: If n contains some prime p more than once as a factor and $SPr(n)$ exists, then the prime q such that n divides $q^* \pm 1$ must be less than p .

Proof: Clear. \square

The next lemma deals with some of the instances where $SPr(n)$ is defined.

Lemma 3: If $n = p_1 p_2 \dots p_k$, where $k \geq 1$ and all p_i are primes, then $SPr(n)$ is defined.

Proof: Let q denote the largest prime factor of n . By definition, q^* contains one instance of all primes less than or equal to q , so n must divide q^* . Given the existence of one such number, there must also be a minimal one. \square

Combining all previous results, we can create a simple algorithm that can be used to determine if $SPr(n)$ exists for any positive integer n .

Input: A positive integer n .

Output: Yes, if $SPr(n)$ exists, No otherwise.

Step 1: Factor n into prime factors, $p_1 p_2 \dots p_k$.

Step 2: If all primes appear to the first power, terminate with the message "Yes".

Step 3: If 2 appears to a power greater than 1, terminate with the message "No".

Step 4: Set $q = 2$, the smallest prime.

Step 5: Compute $q^* + 1$ and $q^* - 1$.

Step 6: If n divides $q^* + 1$ or $q^* - 1$, terminate with the message "Yes".

Step 7: Increment q to the next largest prime.

Step 8: If $q \geq p$, terminate with the message "No".

Step 9: Goto step 5.

And this algorithm can be used to resolve the question mark in the Mudge table. Since 9 does not divide $2^* \pm 1$, $SPr(9)$ is not defined. Furthermore, 3 to any power greater than 2 also cannot divide $2^* \pm 1$, so the conclusion is stronger in that $SPr(n)$ is not defined for n any power of 3 greater than 3.

Note that modifications of this algorithm could be made so that it also returns the value of $SPr(n)$ when defined.

These conclusions can be used to partially answer the third question. The conclusion of lemma 3 concerning all prime factors to the first power is unaffected. However, if $q \geq 3$ and q prime, then $q^* \pm 3$ is also divisible by 3, making solutions possible for higher powers of 3. Such results do indeed occur, as

$$3^* + 3 = 9$$

so that the modified $SPr(9) = 9$.

Reference

1. **The Smarandache Near-To-Primorial Function**, personal correspondence by Michael R. Mudge.